

OpenMod Africa

Data for the Tunisian Energy System

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Table of Contents

List of Tables	5
List of Figures.....	6
List of Abbreviations.....	7
1 Introduction.....	8
2 Model overview and Temporal Scope.....	9
3 Regional Setup and Mapping.....	9
4 Time Series Data and Demand Profiles	11
5 Input Data and Parameter Adaptation.....	17
6 References	25

List of Tables

Table 1 : Regional Classification of Tunisia	10
Table 2 : Regional factories distribution.....	14
Table 3 : Energy demand for each factory.....	14
Table 4 : Monthly Capacity factor	15
Table 5 : Regional modal of transport.....	18
Table 6 : Trade capacity for the year 2022	24

List of Figures

Figure 1: Adopted regional classification of Tunisia	10
Figure 2: Typical hourly profile of passenger mobility by time of year in Tunisia.....	12
Figure 3: 2022 calendar for Tunisia's specific days.....	12
Figure 4 : Regional population data	13
Figure 5 : Hourly Demand profile for Industrial Heat demand	14
Figure 6 : Load profile visualized over all 8760 hours	16
Figure 7 : Load profile visualized over all 24 hours for each month.....	16
Figure 8 : Regional modal transport for mobility passenger and mobility freight.....	22
Figure 9 : Trade between Tunisia's regions	23

List of Abbreviations

GENeSYS-MOD	Global Energy System Model
STEG	Tunisian Company of Electricity and Gas
ANME	Natioanl Agency for Energy and Management
GCT	Tunisian Chemical Group
INS	National Institute of Statistics

1 Introduction

This document provides additional information on the different data components that need to be classified and adapted to configure the GENeSYS-MOD data files for the Tunisian case study.

The first section presents an overview of the model and the temporal scope. The second section outlines the spatial scope: regions and map used in our analysis. The third section focuses on parameters related to hourly data. Lastly, the input datasets and model parameters are adjusted to reflect the specific structural, operational, technological and economic characteristics of the Tunisian energy system, as documented in the input data file.

For reference, all relevant files (hourly and input files) can be accessed at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16736000>

The complete documentation of GENeSYS-MOD is available at the following link: <https://genesysmod.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

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2 Model overview and Temporal Scope

The **Global Energy System Model** GENeSYS-MOD is a linear, cost-minimizing energy system model that adopts a bottom-up approach and is openly available under an open-source license. It has been developed to support long-term transition pathways. The model covers multiple sectors and explicitly addresses emission reduction targets, the integration of renewable energy sources, and sector coupling. Thanks to its modular and scalable structure, the model has been applied to energy systems at both macro-regional and global scales. The optimization process seeks to minimize an objective function representing the total discounted system costs over the entire simulation horizon.

The year 2022 has been selected as the base year, as it provides a more representative and stable energy profile for Tunisia. In contrast, the year 2020 was excluded due to its atypical nature, significantly influenced by the global COVID-19 pandemic, which caused abnormal variations in energy demand and supply patterns.

The modelling horizon spans the period 2022–2050, with results computed at five-year intervals. Accordingly, the years included in the model are: 2022, 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040, 2045, and 2050.

3 Regional Setup and Mapping

Tunisia is administratively divided into 24 governorates. However, due to the limited availability of disaggregated data at the governorate level—particularly in the energy and power sectors, where most statistics are reported by power distribution districts—The present study adopts the regional classification used by the Tunisian Company of Electricity and Gas (STEG), which groups the country into seven broader regions [1]. This aggregation enables more coherent analysis, facilitates data interpretation, and supports strategic energy planning. The map of Figure 1 illustrates the regional classification of Tunisia based on the distribution of energy systems, as defined in Table 1.

Regions considered in this study are located within Tunisia. The interconnections of Tunisia with neighbouring countries such as Algeria and Italy (ELMED Project), are not included in the current version of the study. These regions and connections will be incorporated in a future version.

Table 1 : Regional Classification of Tunisia

Region Code	Region Name	Included Governorates
TN-TN	Greater Tunis (TN)	Ariana, Ben Arous, Manouba, Tunis
TN-NO	North West Tunisia	Beja, Jendouba, kef, siliana
TN-N	North Tunisia	Bizerte, Nabeul, Zaghouan
TN-C	Center Tunisia	Sousse, Monastir, Mahdia, Kairouan
TN-S	South Tunisia	Gabès, Kebili, Medenine, Tataouine
TN-SO	South West Tunisia	Gafsa, Kasserine, Sidi Bouzid, Tozeur
TN-SF	Sfax region	Sfax

Figure 1: Adopted regional classification of Tunisia

4 Time Series Data and Demand Profiles

The GENeSYS-MOD model requires a set of hourly input parameters to accurately represent the dynamics of an energy system across a full year.

In order to adapt the GENeSYS-MOD hourly dataset to the Tunisian case study, several predefined parameters and data sheets must be filled. These parameters can be categorized based on their data source into two categories.

Most of the parameters are generated using the ATLITE package and some parameters' values employ original datasets such as TS_MOBILITY_PASSENGER, TS_HEAT_HIGH, TS_HYDRO_ROR and TS_LOAD.

According to the GENeSYS-MOD hourly data guide [2], four parameters must be filled using original data sources. For the Tunisia case study, two parameters among the four are estimated, namely TS_MOBILITY_PSNG and TS_HEAT_HIGH. While the TS_HYDRO_ROR and TS_LOAD are obtained statistically.

■ TS_MOBILITY_PSNG

This time series represents passenger mobility (demand profile) throughout the year, illustrating the relative volume of passengers for each hour compared to the rest of the hours.

To estimate hourly mobility passenger for the Tunisian case study, the base year (2022) was divided into four distinct day categories: **normal days**, **summer days**, **public holidays** and **Ramadan days** to capture the variability in transport demand throughout the year. This classification is aligned with Tunisian socio-professional habits and cultural practices.

- **Normal days:** During most of the year, the typical workday is split into double work periods (morning and afternoon).
- **Summer days (July and August):** Due to high temperatures and administrative adjustments, most workplaces adopt a single continuous shift, generally from 08:00 to 14:00 or 15:00, leading to earlier mobility peaks.
- **Ramadan days:** During the holy month of Ramadan, working hours are generally reduced and concentrated in a single morning shift like summer period to accommodate fasting practices.
- **Public holidays:** National holidays and weekend days are generally associated with the closure of most workplaces. This closure leads to a significant decrease in commuting-related mobility. However, leisure and mobility often increase, particularly during festive periods. As a result, **hourly passenger mobility tends to shift, with peak demand occurring later in the day and with higher mid-day activity**, especially in areas with high concentrations of commercial, or touristic facilities.

Figure 2 illustrates the variation in hourly passenger mobility for the four defined temporal periods: normal days, summer days, Ramadan days, and public holidays.

Figure 2: Typical hourly profile of passenger mobility by time of year in Tunisia

Figure 3 shows the 2022 calendar identifying the distribution of these day types throughout the year.

2022

Figure 3: 2022 calendar for Tunisia's specific days

At the regional level, hourly passenger mobility was estimated based on the population distribution across the regions, assuming that passenger transport demand is proportional to the local population size [3]. Therefore, it's important to consider the regional population data shown in the histogram below (figure 4). This estimation is based on the work on Estonia [4] with an adaptation to the Tunisian case study. This approach provides an approximation of both spatial and temporal variations in transport across the national territory.

Figure 4 : Regional population data

■ TS_HEAT_HIGH

TS_HEAT_HIGH represents the Time Series for Industrial Heat demand above 1000 °C. It represents the hourly variation in heat demand throughout the year, reflecting the relative share of heat demand for each hour compared to other hours.

Due to limited data availability, a set of assumptions were made to construct this profile.

First, we identified factories requiring high-temperature heat in each region. Tunisia includes five major industries requiring process heat above 1000°C (Cement, steel, glass, chemical and pottery factories). The regional distribution of these factories across the country is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 : Regional factories distribution

Region	Factories
TN-TN	Cement + steel + glass + pottery
TN-N	Cement + steel + glass + chemical + pottery
TN-NO	Steel + cement
TN-C	Cement + glass + pottery
TN-SF	Glass + chemical
TN-SO	Cement + chemical + pottery
TN-S	Chemical

Based on this distribution, we estimated the corresponding electricity consumption profiles for each factory. The energy demand data and the hourly demand profile for each factory are presented, respectively, in table 3 and figure 5. These were obtained from the Tunisian companies ANME [5], STEG [6] and GCT [7].

Table 3 : Energy demand for each factory

Industries	Energy demand (GW)
Cement	0,71917808
Steel	0,05136986
Glass	0,03424658
Pottery	0,02283105
Chemical	0,11415525

Figure 5 : Hourly Demand profile for Industrial Heat demand

The profiles in Figure 5 were adjusted using the geographic distribution of industries to reflect the spatial concentration of high temperature heat demand. This approach enabled the refinement of the TS_HEAT input dataset by aligning it with regional industrial activity.

■ TS_HYDRO_ROR

This time series represents the capacity factor for hydroelectric power plants. The capacity factor for run-of-river hydroelectric plants can vary significantly depending on site-specific conditions, such as river flow consistency and plant design.

The capacity factor was calculated using historical data on installed capacity [7] and actual energy production based on the following formula provided in the hourly data guide [2]:

$$\text{Capacity Factor} = \frac{\text{Actual Energy Production (MWh)}}{\text{Installed Capacity (MW)} \times \text{Time}}$$

To account for seasonal, weekly, or daily variations—depending on the level of detail in the available data—the capacity factor can be adjusted accordingly. Due to limited data availability, we chose to calculate and represent monthly variability by assigning the same value to each day within a given month, as presented in Table 4.

Table 4 : Monthly Capacity factor

Month	Energy Produced (GWh)	Installed Capacity (GW)	Hours in month
January	0,2	0,0625	744
February	0,9	0,0625	672
March	1	0,0625	744
April	0,8	0,0625	720
May	1,8	0,0625	744
June	2,6	0,0625	720
July	2,7	0,0625	744
August	2,2	0,0625	744
September	1,1	0,0625	720
October	0,6	0,0625	744
Novemeber	0,5	0,0625	720
December	0,6	0,0625	744

■ TS_LOAD

This time series represents the hourly demand profile throughout the year, showing the relative share of power consumption at each hour. All data used in this analysis were obtained directly from the Tunisian Company of Electricity and Gas [6]. Figure 6 illustrates the full-year load profile across all 8760 hours.

Figure 6 : Load profile visualized over all 8760 hours

Figure 7 provides a detailed daily variation of the load profiles evolve throughout the year.

Figure 7 : Load profile visualized over all 24 hours for each month

5 Input Data and Parameter Adaptation

The input data file in GENeSYS-MOD defines the key parameters and constraints of the Tunisian energy system within the model. These include technology-specific parameters such as capital costs, fixed and variable costs, efficiency, operational life, and availability of different energy technologies, as well as renewable resource potentials. Energy demand data are disaggregated by sector with appropriate yearly time resolution. Information on resource availability, associated costs, and import/export options is also included. Economic and policy parameters, such as discount rates, emission targets, and carbon pricing are implemented to reflect the Tunisian context.

The spatial structure is defined through regional disaggregation and interregional trade capacities. All input data are organized and calibrated to represent Tunisia's specific energy system, allowing the model to find the most cost-effective development pathways over the defined time horizon.

All tagged parameters remain constant across different case studies, meaning they do not vary from one case study to another. Conversely, parameters that differ between case studies are sourced from a wide range of reputable references to ensure accuracy and contextual relevance.

Building on the classification of parameters, Key data for variable parameters are obtained from national institutions such as the Ministry of Mines and Energy, the National Agency for Energy Management (ANME), the Tunisian Electricity and Gas Company (STEG), the Ministry of Transport, and the National Institute of Statistics (INS). In addition, environmental authorities provide essential information on emission targets and policies. Supplementary data are gathered from official reports, peer-reviewed scientific articles, and publicly accessible databases. This comprehensive approach to data sourcing enhances the robustness and reliability of simulation results for Tunisia's energy system.

Most of the data sources and assumptions used in this study are documented in the excel file available on the shared drive at the following link :

<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1LGPYuPHvaUzrFf7NLph6dUMLdkNp8OPv> .

Base year data (2022) are derived from historical records such as official statistics and measured energy system parameters. However, Future projections are based on Tunisia's Strategic plans, national strategies and scenario-based extrapolations grounded in historical trends. Additionally when necessary, projected data are generated through interpolation methods to ensure a consistent temporal resolution throughout the modeling time horizon.

For certain parameters where detailed regional data is unavailable, we applied informed assumptions. For instance, regarding passenger mobility, the exact number of vehicles per region is not available. Therefore

we estimated this value based on different indicators such as population density, industrial activity, degree of urbanization and other socio-economic parameters relevant to regional mobility patterns.

Similarly, for regional base year production, while total generation per region and the overall production mix by technology at the national level are available, detailed data on the specific production amounts by technology within each region are lacking. To address this gap, we assumed that the production mix by technology in each region is proportional to the existing residual generation capacities. This approach enabled us to estimate technology-specific electricity production at the regional level for the base year.

Hydropower plants have been excluded from the scope of this study, as their contribution to Tunisia's overall energy production is extremely limited and their inclusion causes infeasibilities during model simulations.

In general, two parameters are estimated and incorporated within the input data file to represent the energy system dynamics: `Par_ModalSplitByFuel` and `Par_Trade Capacity`.

■ **ModalSplitByFuel:**

This parameter defines the distribution of technologies across different modal types. The model considers two main fuel categories: Passenger Transport and Freight Transport, each associated with a specified annual demand. Within each category, different technologies (referred to as `ModalTypes`) are available to meet this demand. The **ModalSplitByFuel** parameter specifies the minimum share of each technology within its respective fuel category.

A summary of the major transport modes across the seven regions is provided in table 5.

Currently, only passenger rail transport is powered by electricity [1, 6], whereas all other transport modes remain dependent on conventional fossil fuels. This highlights the limited penetration of low-carbon technologies in the current transport mix. Figure 8 illustrates the regional distribution of transport modes for both passenger and freight mobility in 2022.

Table 5 : Regional modal of transport

Region	Modal of transport
TN-TN	rail + road + air
TN-C	rail + road + air
TN-SF	rail + road + air + ship
TN-NO	rail + road + air
TN-S	rail + road + air + ship
TN-N	rail + road
TN-SO	rail + road + air

MOBILITY FREIGHT

MOBILITY PASSENGER

MOBILITY FREIGHT

MOBILITY PASSENGER

MOBILITY FREIGHT

Ship 0 % Rail 4 % Air 1 %

Road 95 %

MOBILITY PASSENGER

Ship 0 % Rail 1 % Air 0 %

Road 99 %

MOBILITY FREIGHT

Ship 4 % Rail 20 % Air 1 %

Road 75 %

MOBILITY PASSENGER

Ship 0 % Rail 29 % Air 1 %

Road 70 %

Figure 8 : Regional modal transport for mobility passenger and mobility freight

For the future projections, the adopted model assumes that renewable energy will account for 35% of modal transport energy consumption by 2030, with this share increasing to 50% by 2050 [5]. These percentages correspond to the renewables share in the electricity production and are based on total electrification of transportation. This progression reflects a gradual but significant transition towards sustainable mobility solutions driven by energy decarbonization policies a technological advancement in the transport sector.

■ Trade Capacity:

Trade capacities represent the capacity of trade between neighboring regions, trade Capacity for power are given in GW and trade capacity for Gas, H2 etc. are given in PJ. They are defined for each year and represent the currently available trade capacities and consider their expected lifetime.

For the Tunisian case study, the national electricity system is modelled as centralized in the Tunis region (TN-TN), reflecting the operational reality of the Tunisian Company of Electricity and Gaz (STEG) [1, 6]. STEG is a state-owned monopoly responsible for the generation, distribution and sale of electricity and natural gas in Tunisia, Operating through a single national grid. We assume that electricity production from

all regions is aggregated in the Tunis region, which acts as the central hub, before being distributed to the rest of the country according to regional demand for both electricity and gas (see Figure 9).

Figure 9 : Trade between Tunisia's regions

To ensure the model runs effectively, the trade capacity between Tunisia's regions is configured so that power inflows and outflows are balanced (see table 6). Compared to the annual demand, the trade capacity is set slightly higher to make the program run without infeasibilities.

Region	Region2	Fuel	Year	Value
TN-TN	TN-N	Power	2022	6,183409
TN-TN	TN-SF	Power	2022	2,974378
TN-TN	TN-SO	Power	2022	5,626903
TN-TN	TN-NO	Power	2022	2,16895
TN-TN	TN-S	Power	2022	3,461124
TN-TN	TN-C	Power	2022	6,820776
TN-C	TN-TN	Power	2022	6,820776
TN-N	TN-TN	Power	2022	6,183409
TN-SF	TN-TN	Power	2022	2,974378
TN-SO	TN-TN	Power	2022	5,626903
TN-NO	TN-TN	Power	2022	2,16895
TN-S	TN-TN	Power	2022	3,461124

Table 6 : Trade capacity for the year 2022

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